

IV. PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE WITH PIPELINE

Fig.3 pipeline architecture of 8 bit Pico Processor

4.1 Instruction Fetch Unit

The first stage in the pipeline is the Instruction Fetch. Instructions are fetched from the memory and the Instruction Pointer (IP) is updated. The function of the instruction fetch unit is to obtain an instruction from the instruction memory using the current value of the PC and increment the PC value for the next instruction as shown in Figure. This stage is where a program counter will pull the next instruction from the correct location in program memory. In addition the program counter will be updated with either the next instruction location sequentially, or the instruction location as determined by a branch. The instruction fetch stage is also responsible for reading the instruction memory and sending the current instruction to the next stage in the pipeline, or a stall if a branch has been detected in order to avoid incorrect execution. The instruction fetch unit contains the following logic elements that are implemented in VHDL: 12-bit program counter (PC) register, an adder to increment the PC by four, the instruction memory, a multiplexor, and an AND gate used to select the value of the next PC. Program counter and instruction memory are the two important blocks of Instructions Fetch Unit.^{[1][2]}

4.1.1 Program counters (PC): It is a 12 bit device that is connected to the data bus and the address bus. It will hold its value unless told to do something. If the I/P is kept high the device will count.

4.1.2 Instruction memory (IM): The Instruction memory of pP is of 4KB. During the Instruction Fetch stage, a 19-bit instruction is fetched from the memory. The PC predictor sends the Program Counter (PC) to the Instruction memory to read the current Instruction. At the same time, the PC predictor predicts the address of the next instruction by incrementing the PC by 1.

4.1.3 Instruction registers (IR): An instruction register (IR) is the part of control unit that stores the instruction currently

being executed or decoded. In simple processors each instruction to be executed is loaded into the instruction register which holds it while it is decoded, prepared and ultimately executed, which can take several steps. Traditional RISC processors use a pipeline of instruction registers where each stage of the pipeline does part. Of the decoding, preparation or execution and then passes it to the next stage for its step. Modern processors can even do some of the steps out of order as decoding on several instructions is done in parallel. Decoding the op-code in the instruction register includes determining the instruction, where its operands are in memory, retrieving the operands from memory, allocating processor resources to execute the command. The output of IR is available to control circuits which generate the timing signals that controls the various processing elements involved in executing the instruction.

4.2 Instruction Decode Unit

The Instruction Decode stage is the second stage in the pipeline. Branch targets will be calculated here and the Register File, the dual-port memory containing the register values, resides in this stage. The forwarding units, solving the data hazards in the pipeline, reside here. Their function is to detect if the register to be fetched in this stage is written to in a later stage. In that case the data is forward to this stage and the data hazard is solved. This stage is where the control unit determines what values the control lines must be set to depending on the instruction. In addition, hazard detection is implemented in this stage, and all necessary values are fetched from the register banks. The Decode Stage is the stage of the CPU's pipeline where the fetched instruction is decoded, and values are fetched from the register bank. It is responsible for mapping the different sections of the instruction into their proper representations (based on R or I type instructions). The Decode stage consists of the Control unit, the Hazard Detection Unit, the Sign Extender, and the Register bank, and is responsible for connecting all of these components together. It splits the instruction into its various parts and feeds them to the corresponding components. Registers Rs and Rt are fed to the register bank, the immediate section is fed to the sign extender, and the ALU op-code and function codes are sent to the control unit. The outputs of these corresponding components are then clocked and stored for the next stage. The Control unit takes the given op-code, as well as the function code from the instruction, and translates it to the individual instruction control lines needed by the three remaining stages. This is accomplished via a large case statement.

4.2.1 Control unit: The control unit of the Pico processor examines the instruction op code bits [19 – 14] and decodes the instruction to generate control signals to be used in the additional modules. The RegDst control signal determines which register is written to the register file. The Jump control signal selects the jump address to be sent to the PC. The Branch control signal is used to select the branch address to be sent to the PC. The MemRead control signal is asserted during a load instruction when the data memory is read to load a register with its memory contents. The MemtoReg control

signal determines if the ALU result or the data memory output is written to the register file. The ALUOp control signals determine the function the ALU performs. (E.g. and, or, add, shl, shr) The MemWrite control signal is asserted when during a store instruction when a registers value is stored in the data memory. The ALUSrc control signal determines if the ALU second operand comes from the register file or the sign extend. The RegWrite control signal is asserted when the register file needs to be written.

4.2.2 Register files (RF): During the decode stage, the two register Rs & Rt are identified within the instruction, and the two registers are read from the register file. In this design, the register file is of 8X8 size (namely r0 to r7) which had 8 entries. At the same time the register file was read, instruction issue logic in this stage determined if the pipeline was ready to execute the instruction in this stage. If not, the issue logic would cause both the Instruction Fetch stage and the Decode stage to stall. If the instruction decoded was a branch or jump, the target address of the branch or jump was computed in parallel with reading the register file. The branch condition is computed after the register file is read, and if the branch is taken or if the instruction is a jump; the PC predictor in the first stage is assigned the branch target, rather than the incremented PC that has been computed.

4.3 Execution Unit: The third stage in the pipeline is where the arithmetic- and logic-instructions will be executed. All instructions are executed with 8-bit operands and the result is a 8-bit word. The execution unit of the pP processor contains the arithmetic logic unit (ALU) which performs the operation determined by the ALUop signal. The branch address is calculated by adding the PC+1 to the sign extended immediate field shifted left 2 bits by a separate adder. The logic elements to be implemented in VHDL.

4.3.1 ALU unit: The arithmetic/logic unit (ALU) executes all arithmetic and logical operations. The arithmetic/logic unit can perform four kinds of arithmetic operations, or mathematical calculations: addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division. As its name implies, the arithmetic/logic unit also performs logical operations. A logical operation is usually a comparison. The unit can compare numbers, letters, or special characters. The computer can then take action based on the result of the comparison. This is a very important capability.

4.4 Memory Access unit

The memory access stage is the fourth stage of pipeline. This is where load and store instructions will access data memory. During this stage, single cycle latency instructions simply have their results forwarded to the next stage. This forwarding ensures that both single and two cycle instructions always write their results in the same stage of the pipeline, so that just one write port to the register file can be used, and it is always Available. If the instruction is a load, the data is read from the data memory.

4.4.1 Data Memory Unit (DM): The data memory unit is only accessed by the load and store instructions. The load instruction asserts the MemRead signal and uses the ALU Result value as an address to index the data memory. The read

output data is then subsequently written into the register file. A store instruction asserts the MemWrite signal and writes the data value previously read from a register into the computed memory address.

4.5 Write back unit

During this stage, both single cycle and multi cycle instructions write their results into the register file.

V. VARIOUS HAZARDS IN PIPELINE

Although with the help of pipeline we can increase the clock rate and overall throughput of a processor but during the process the following hazards may occur^[1]

5.1 Structural hazards: - It arises from resources conflict when the hardware cannot support all possible combinations of instructions simultaneously in overlapped execution. It can be handled by using separate memories one for data and one for instructions.

5.2 Data Hazards: - When an instruction depends on the results of a previous instruction in a way that is exposed by the overlapping of instructions in the pipeline. It can be handled by using data forwarding.

5.3 Control Hazards:- It arises from the pipelining of branches and other instruction that change the PC.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

With the help of pipeline architecture mentioned above overall throughput of the pP can be increased. As far as result is concerned a basic 8 bit microprocessor having clock rate of 2 MHz and consists 6000 transistors achieve the MIPS of 0.64 (INTEL 8080). So upon pipelining the Pico processor should achieve greater MIPS than above. With this kind of improve performance pP can be used for small embedded applications as well as for educational purpose.

Future work will be added by increasing the number of instructions and to add more pipelined stages in the design to improve the performance of the design and to increase the speed of the processor.

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